

Priority Directions for Reforming the Banking System in the Republic of Uzbekistan

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Abstract: This article discusses issues concerning the goal of the banking system reform strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025 and priorities to implement comprehensive changes in the banking system aimed at forming a modern banking system, increasing the investment attractiveness of banks, and introducing new standards of banking services.

Key points: banking system, banking sector, lending, deposit operations, priorities, modern standards, market conditions, financial support.

One of the main directions of the reform of the banking sector is to reduce the dependence of banks on state resources, to automate the activities of banks, to gradually cancel the functions of banks that are not related to the main type of activity, and to increase the efficiency of the banking system.

The strategy of reforming the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5953 of March 2, 2020, five priority directions for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021. In accordance with the state program for the implementation of the Action Strategy in the "Year of Development of Science, Enlightenment and Digital Economy", as well as taking into account the main conclusions and recommendations of the World Bank on the results of the study of the current state of the country's banking system developed.

The strategy defines the goals, tasks and priority areas of the development of the banking system, directions for transformation and reform of the banking system in 2020-2025, ways to search for possible solutions based on the experience of transforming the financial sector of foreign countries and taking into account world trends in the financial sector.

Today, the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan consists of 31 commercial banks (hereinafter referred to as banks) that provide traditional banking services such as lending, deposit operations, settlement and cash.

During the period of our country's independence, banks were established for specific purposes and tasks, actively involving them in financing state-owned enterprises and state development programs at preferential interest rates. As a result, the share of preferential loans in the total portfolio of the banking system is more than 60 percent.

The state has a dominant position in the banking sector - 13 out of 31 banks have state participation in their capital, their capital is more than 87% of the total capital of the banking system, and their assets are more than 85% of total assets.

In 2019, a number of qualitative changes were made in the banking system. In particular:

- Adoption of the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Banks and Banking Activities" and "On the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan" in a new version, which are in line with modern standards and principles of banking;
- Reform of financing mechanisms of investment projects with the participation of the Reconstruction and Development Fund of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- abandoning the practice of lending state programs at rates lower than the main rate of the Central Bank and transitioning to market conditions of lending from 2021;
- within the framework of the state targeted programs for the development of entrepreneurship, the concentration of lending in 3 banks - AT Xalq Bank, "Agrobank" ADB and "Mikrokreditbank" ADB;
- organization of the mechanism of preferential financial support of entrepreneurial activities by the state through the State Fund for the Support of Entrepreneurial Activities;
- introduction of a new procedure for providing the population with housing at the expense of mortgage loans based on market principles;
- Assessment of prudential control mechanisms and procedures over the activities of commercial banks in cooperation with the World Bank from the point of view of their compliance with the principles of the Basel Committee.

The dominant position of the state in the banking sector, the active involvement of banks as intermediaries for financing various state programs and enterprises, has led to some problems.

The goal of the banking system reform strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025 is to implement comprehensive changes in the banking system aimed at forming a modern banking system, increasing the investment attractiveness of banks, and introducing new standards of banking services.

The following are the priority directions of reforming the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

- creation of equal competitive conditions in the financial market, lending only based on market requirements, reducing the dependence of banks on state resources, modernization of banking services, creation of efficient infrastructure and automation of bank operations, as well as phasing of functions of banks that are not related to the main type of activity - increase the efficiency of the banking system by canceling the phase;
- improving the quality of the credit portfolio and the quality of risk management, following a moderate level of credit growth, conducting a balanced macroeconomic policy, improving corporate governance and attracting managers with practical experience at the international level, implementing technological solutions for assessing financial risks ensuring the financial stability of the banking system through;
- comprehensive transformation of commercial banks with a state share, introduction of modern banking standards, information technologies and software products, sale of state shares in banks to investors with the necessary experience and knowledge on the basis of competitive bidding, as well as with a state share reducing the share of the state in the banking sector by simultaneously reforming commercial banks and enterprises;
- increase state participation and implementation of targeted measures in insufficiently served and vulnerable groups, wide introduction of remote services for the population and small businesses, development of a network of low-cost service points, as well as in the unified financial system of the republic increasing the popularity and quality of financial services by creating favorable conditions for the formation and development of non-bank credit organizations as a mutually complementary part.

Improving the efficiency of the banking system is the most important factor of economic development in order to ensure the growing needs of business entities and citizens for affordable and high-quality financial services.

In this regard, it is planned to implement the following measures within the framework of the Strategy:

- 1) to expand the scope and improve the quality of banking services due to the involvement of advanced international experience and technologies;
- 2) improvement of management in banks by introducing advanced standards and experience of corporate management, ensuring transparency of the accountability and activity of bank management bodies and proper disclosure of information by them;
- 3) abandoning subsidized lending in order to increase the commercialization of banks' activities, ensure the financial stability of the banking system, as well as increase the effectiveness of monetary policy instruments;
- 4) increasing the role of commercial banks as financial intermediaries that ensure the mobilization of savings for investments and directing them to finance the most effective sectors from a financial and economic point of view;
- 5) consistent liberalization of banking activities and harmonization with the best international practice in order to create the necessary conditions for attracting strategic foreign investors and ensuring the gradual integration of the financial system into the international financial markets;
- 6) creation of favorable conditions for the development of non-bank credit organizations, including the development of competition in this segment, through the development of appropriate norms of prudential regulation, as well as the ease of access to financial services.

The financial stability and durability of the banking sector is the main condition for the successful implementation of the planned reforms and strengthening the trust of business and the population in the national banking system.

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